

Piloting the Application of a Controlled Vocabulary to an OSF-Hosted Repository: The Case of REPOPSI

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This report was created as part of the project titled “TRUST-ification and FAIR-ification of an open repository for research instruments in psychology: REPOPSI's adoption of RDA outputs”, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017536. The project has received support from the [EOSC Future](#) through the [RDA Open Call mechanism](#), based on evaluations of external, independent experts.

About the Repository

REPOPSI (www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/) is an open repository for psychological measures, scales, tests, and other research instruments in Serbian. It is maintained by researchers at the Laboratory for Research of Individual Differences ([LIRA](#)) at the University of Belgrade Faculty of Philosophy. REPOPSI instruments are deposited in an Open Science Framework (OSF) project at osf.io/5zb8p/.

Problem Statement

At the start of the project, the psychological instruments in the REPOPSI repository were described with two metadata sets. The shortcomings of these metadata sets limit REPOPSI's Interoperability and Reusability (source: [REPOPSI Start-Project Evaluation Using the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model](#) from December 2022).

One metadata set can be found in tabular REPOPSI_inventory CSV (osf.io/mxrc2/) and XLSX (osf.io/2j7y8/) files deposited on the OSF, as well as in a [Google spreadsheet](#) (which is, since July 2023, searchable using an [interactive web app](#)). The main problem with the tabular file is that it is not supported by any metadata standard.

The other metadata set is embedded alongside the instruments in their respective OSF component (see, for example, osf.io/2pxmg/). The OSF metadata fields used to describe the instruments are: title (free-text input), identifier (DOI), and publication and modification dates (generated automatically following the ISO 8601 standard). Each OSF component has a number of specific and accurate “tags” manually added to it, enhancing its discoverability ([Tag Your Project - OSF Support](#)). However, these free-text metatags are not standardised and are not FAIR-compliant (that is, they do not meet the principles of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability). Furthermore, some of the fields from the REPOPSI tabular metadata file are not supported by the OSF metadata structure. For instance, all of the REPOPSI contents are available under the Creative Commons Attribution - NoCommercial - ShareAlike 4.0 International (CC BY-NC-SA 4.0) licence. However, this type of Creative Commons licence is unavailable in OSF rights options ([Licensing - OSF Support](#)). The second Interoperability principle states that metadata should use vocabularies that follow the FAIR principles ([FAIR Data Maturity Model](#)). However, OSF does not currently have the infrastructure to connect and use a controlled vocabulary. While OSF has recently implemented some metadata enhancements to improve the FAIR-ness of OSF content ([New OSF Metadata to Support Data Sharing Policy Compliance](#) blog post), the new metadata fields they added cannot be integrated with REPOPSI.

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Solution

In order to put REPOPSI metadata into a machine-readable format, we decided to develop a computer code using the [Python programming language](#). The code uses the REPOPSI_inventory tabular CSV file to generate an XML metadata document in compliance with the latest version of the [DataCite Metadata Schema](#) (Version 4.4). These XML documents have been deposited into OSF components of every instrument currently available in REPOPSI, providing fully enriched and standardised metadata for every Repository item. Due to their machine readability, the XML documents can be used for migration purposes if the REPOPSI team decides to change the Repository platform. For an example, see the following component osf.io/2pxmg/, with the deposited XML document (osf.io/n5deh/).

For every psychological instrument, the Python code generates an XML document with much richer metadata than OSF could provide. For example, it has an embedded usage licence in a machine readable format, which is in compliance with the principle of Reusability. To address the Interoperability issues, the REPOPSI team decided to include an additional column in the tabular metadata file ("*LCSH terminology*.") with values defined by the terms of a FAIR-compliant vocabulary. For this purpose, the [Library of Congress Subject Headings \(LCSH\)](#) controlled vocabulary was chosen. We decided to, for now, apply only one term – "[Psychological tests](#)". Compared to OSF metatags, this term is broader and therefore not as useful to REPOPSI users. However, since a lot of the REPOPSI data and metadata have already been created, adding more terms would have been a time-consuming process.

The LCSH vocabulary is widely used for describing the information resources and has features that are compatible with the FAIR principles:

- Every subject term is declared with a unique and persistent identifier in a form of a URI string (Findability principle);
- The vocabulary is always available through HTTP standardised internet protocol (Accessibility principle);
- Vocabulary terms are described with a formal, machine-readable and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation, i.e. Resource Description Framework (RDF) (Interoperability and Reusability principles);
- Vocabulary is freely available for reuse under a public domain licence (Reusability principle).

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This solution improves the overall FAIR-ness of the Repository, particularly the principles that were not marked as “fully implemented” during the [REPOPSI Start-Project Evaluation Using the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model](#) in December 2022. In particular, the following FAIR principles have been enhanced:

- F3 - Metadata includes the identifier for the data;
- I2 - Metadata uses FAIR-compliant vocabularies;
- I3 - Metadata includes references to other (meta)data;
- R1.1 - Metadata refers to a machine-understandable reuse licence.

An Overview of the XML Metadata Document

The table below provides an overview of the DataCite XML fields alongside the values of the REPOPSI_inventory tabular CSV file that are being parsed. The fields that are mandatory in the DataCite Metadata Schema are coloured in red.

DataCite XML field	REPOPSI_inventory.csv column
<identifier identifierType="DOI">	Link to instrument in the Repository.
<alternateIdentifier alternateIdentifierType="URL">	Link to instrument in the Repository.
<publisher>	Value is :tba (predefined value for unknown data or when they need to be decided; from the DataCite Metadata Schema , Appendix 3: Standard values for unknown information).
<publicationYear>	source: <i>DataCite API</i> For the instruments that have a DOI persistent identifier from the OSF platform, it is possible to extract registered metadata with the DataCite Commons API.
<creators> <creator><creatorName nameType="Personal">	Citation of the original instrument. The authors are extracted with the use of regular expressions.
<titles>	Title in English. Title in Serbian. (<title xml:lang="sr" titleType="AlternativeTitle">) Abbreviation. (<title titleType="Other">)

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<subjects>

Keywords.

Free-form metatags.

LCSH terminology.

A column to connect metadata with the controlled vocabulary terms (in this case, with the LCSH terms)

<contributors>

Citation of the translation/adaptation.

<contributor contributorType="Other">

For *contributorType* attributes there is no predefined value for translators, so we use the value *Other*.

<rights

License.

rightsURI="https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/" rightsIdentifier="CC-BY-NC-SA-4.0" rightsIdentifierScheme="SPDX" schemeURI="https://spdx.org/licenses/">

<description descriptionType="Abstract">

Abstract.

<description descriptionType="Other">

Version.

Available languages.

Citation of the original instrument.

Source of the original instrument.

Citation of the translation/adaptation.

Source of the translation/adaptation.

Contact person.

Contact email address.

<relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="DOI" relationType="IsPartOf">

The permanent value is *DOI: 10.17605/OSF.IO/5ZB8P*, because the instrument is part of the REPOPSI repository.

<relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="DOI" relationType="IsMetadataFor">

Link to instrument in the Repository.

This relates the XML metadata with the particular psychological instrument with a DOI persistent identifier.

<resourceType resourceTypeGeneral="Text">

The value is always *Component*.

Python Code Availability

The Python code for generating XML documents with enriched REPOPSI metadata is available on Zenodo under the free and open licence ([Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/)) at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8150869>.

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